

DELIVERABLE

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Data Management Plan

D6.2

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PROJECT SUMMARY

Addressing the grand challenges that the world is facing nowadays in connection with energy, information and health requires the development of unconventional methods for unprecedented visualization of matter. SMART-electron aims to develop an innovative technological platform for designing, realizing and operating all-optical rapidly-programmable phase masks for electrons. By introducing a new paradigm where properly synthesized ultrafast electromagnetic fields will be used for engineering the phase space of a free-electron wave function, we will be able to achieve unprecedented space/time/energy/momentum shaping of electron matter waves, surpassing conventional passive monolithic schemes and revolutionizing the way materials are investigated in electron microscopy. Such unique high-speed, flexible and precise full-phase multidimensional control, will enable novel advanced imaging approaches in electron microscopy with enhanced features, such as higher image-resolution, lower electron dose, faster acquisition rate, higher signal-to-noise ratio, and three-dimensional image reconstruction, together with higher temporal resolution and high energy-momentum sensitivity. In SMART-electron, we will make such potential a reality by implementing for the first time three beyond-the-state-of-the-art imaging techniques enabled by our photonic-based electron modulators, namely: (1) Ramsey-type Holography, (2) Electron Single-Pixel Imaging, and (3) Quantum Cathodoluminescence. Such new approaches will lead to unprecedented visualization of many-body states in quantum materials, real-time electrochemical reactions, and spatio-temporal localization of biomimetic nanoparticles in cells for drug delivery. By surpassing the current paradigms in terms of electron manipulation, the project has the potential to drive electron microscopy into a new and exciting age where scientists will benefit from new tools with unprecedented performances that were unimaginable until now.

LIST OF BENEFICIARIES

Beneficiary	Legal Entity Short Name	Country
Università degli Studi Di Milano-Bicocca	UNIMIB	IT
Ecole Polytechnique Federale de Lausanne	EPFL	CH
Fundacio Institut de Ciencies Fotoniques	ICFO	SP
Technion – Israel Institute of Technology	TECHNION	IL
Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	CNR	IT
Holoeye Photonics AG	HOLOEYE	DE
QED Film & Stage Productions LTD	QED	UK

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The DMP has the objective to describe the lifecycle of all data to be generated, collected, processed and stored during the project and how data will be shared after the project's end. Internal practices per partner, as well as common Consortium practices, should be described.

SMART-electron is a FET-Open project with the aim to develop an innovative technological platform for designing, realizing and operating all-optical rapidly-programmable phase masks for electrons. During the course of the project, SMART-electron will generate a variety of data covering a wide range of R&D and regulation activities: experimental and theoretical results will appear in the form of electron microscopy images, spectra and diffraction patterns, as well as light optical images, spectra and time-correlation profiles.

As far as metadata and data are concerned, the guiding principle is to strive to make them FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) as much as possible.

SMART-electron data will be originated in laboratory environments (experiments) and computing facilities (theory and simulations). In general, the project is expected to generate novel scientific data that will be kept confidential until their publication. Before publication, data will be shared on a collaborative basis within the SMART-electron Consortium.

UPDATES OF THE DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

The Data Management Plan, deliverable D6.2 foreseen at month 6, will be updated by all the project partners. Two internal updates are foreseen in M24 and M36 as by Grant Agreement and will be the result of continuous monitoring by the coordinator.

Besides the updates foreseen by Grant Agreement (at M24 and M36), the DMP will be updated, over the course of the project, whenever significant changes arise, to ensure compliance with Horizon 2020 guidelines. Among these changes it is possible to list: changes in consortium policies or changes in consortium composition and external factors.

Official versions of the DMP will be on the project online repository as PDF files. An editable word copy of the latest version will also be stored on the internal SMART-electron repository, to facilitate revision and update of the already identified datasets and policies.

1 MAKING DATA FAIR

SMART-electron partners will regularly upload the experimental data on the **Zenodo platform** (an OpenAIRE - <https://www.openaire.eu> - and CERN collaboration), which embraces the FAIR Principles as defined in *Wilkinson, M. D. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Sci. Data 3:160018 doi: [10.1038/sdata.2016.18](https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18) (2016).*

Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable data

1.1 TO BE FINDABLE

- **F1:** (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
 - A DOI is issued to every published record on Zenodo.
- **F2:** data are described with rich metadata (defined by point R1 below)
 - Zenodo's metadata is compliant with [DataCite's Metadata Schema](#) minimum and recommended terms, with a few additional enrichments.
- **F3:** metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes
 - The DOI is a top-level and a mandatory field in the metadata of each record.
- **F4:** (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource
 - Metadata of each record is indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing.

Metadata of each record is sent to DataCite servers during DOI registration and indexed there.

1.2 TO BE ACCESSIBLE

- **A1:** (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol
 - Metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the [OAI-PMH](#) protocol by the record identifier and the collection name.
 - Metadata is also retrievable through the public [REST API](#).
- **A1.1:** the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
 - See point A1. OAI-PMH and REST are open, free and universal protocols for information retrieval on the web.
- **A1.2:** the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary
 - Metadata are publicly accessible and licensed under public domain. No authorization is ever necessary to retrieve it.
- **A2:** metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available
 - Data and metadata will be retained for the lifetime of the repository.

Metadata are stored in high-availability database servers at CERN, which are separate to the data itself.

1.3 TO BE INTEROPERABLE

- **I1:** (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.

- Zenodo uses [JSON Schema](#) as internal representation of metadata and offers export to other popular formats such as [Dublin Core](#) or [MARCXML](#).
- **I2:** (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
 - For certain terms we refer to open, external vocabularies, e.g.: license ([Open Definition](#)), funders ([FundRef](#)) and grants ([OpenAIRE](#)).
- **I3:** (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data
 - Each referenced external piece of metadata is qualified by a resolvable URL.

1.4 TO BE REUSABLE

- **R1:** (meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
 - Each record contains a minimum of DataCite's mandatory terms, with optionally additional DataCite recommended terms and Zenodo's enrichments.
- **R1.1:** (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license
 - License is one of the mandatory terms in Zenodo's metadata, and is referring to a [Open Definition](#) license.
 - Data downloaded by the users is subject to the license specified in the metadata by the uploader.
- **R1.2:** (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance
 - All data and metadata uploaded is traceable to a registered Zenodo user.
 - Metadata can optionally describe the original authors of the published work.
- **R1.3:** (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards
 - Zenodo is not a domain-specific repository, yet through compliance with DataCite's Metadata Schema, metadata meets one of the broadest cross-domain standards available.

2 OPEN SCIENCE PRACTICES AND MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES

2.1 OPEN SCIENCE

SMART-electron fully complies with the principles of open science (Figure 1):

(A) Systematic sharing of knowledge and tools as early and widely as possible:

- i) preregistration, registered reports and preprints, will be used whenever applicable;
- ii) measures to ensure reproducibility of research outputs providing open access to research outputs: pending the need of confidentiality and IPR, we will ensure a timely access to research results including data and metadata, to ensure the re-use and reproducibility (see section 2.2 below).

All publications related to SMART-electron will be made Open Access (with Gold option if available), choosing the open peer-reviews when possible. Preprints will be available right before submission to a peer-reviewed journal. See *Chapter 4* below for additional information.

Open access journals will be always preferred for publications, e.g. the newly launched **Open Research Europe**. Data, protocols, software and other tools underlying the publications will be released at the same time via open access repositories (e.g. **ArXiv** or other discipline specific repositories), providing the DOI to the related publication.

(B) Involving all relevant knowledge actors: we will engage relevant target groups, such as European companies and start-ups active in the Microscopy and Photonics field and public policy makers for science and technology and civil society, in the definition of the research future exploitation and dissemination plan, *via* press releases, focus meetings and outreach events.

Figure 1: Schematics of the open science practices.

2.2 DATA MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES

We will manage research data according to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable) principles – as described above in *Chapter 1*, also in the framework of Open Science practices. The following provisions, summarized in Figure 2, will be taken:

- ✓ Our management plan will be based on the principle “**as open as possible, as closed as necessary**”, with details about data types, accessibility, verification and validation. In *Chapter 3* below we will define the best practice workflows and quality assurance procedures, including re-use policy.
- ✓ Implementation of **data lifecycle control** (see *Chapter 3* below). This will include: (a) data specification and processing, database maintenance and security, to ensure that data will be fit for purpose and held securely in their own databases; (b) ongoing data audit, to monitor the use and continued effectiveness of the data; (c) archiving and final destruction, to ensure that data are maintained effectively until they are no longer needed or are uneconomical to retain. Data and all the information that can be extracted from them, will be available to other partners during the project and should be preserved for at least five years after project end, to facilitate post-project result exploitation and future model extensions.
- ✓ Identification of **data ownership and stewardship** to ensure that the right people are assigned to the right roles within the data management system. We will integrate our data management team with our subject matter experts to ensure that **data integrity and quality** is maintained while also making smart decisions about what information needs to be captured. Each partner is responsible for the preservation of data that they generate during the project, by means of state-of-the-art on-site storage hardware or third-party cloud storage server (see *Chapter 4* below).
- ✓ Ensuring **data security** (see *Chapter 5* below). This includes both infrastructure security measures as well as best management practices regarding user access and authority to access various types of data within the system.
- ✓ Establishing **data quality standards** (see *Chapter 3* below). To maximize the potential and use of datasets, partners will: (a) use standard data definitions and formats; (b) define quality standards and apply the appropriate validation processes to each dataset; (c) adopt formal query and change management procedures; (d) ensure that data are quality assured and approved as fit for purpose before use or release. Due to the high variability of data generated,

each partner will be asked to store data for preservation in a format that can ensure **portability**, preferring standard open-source format to proprietary or discontinued formats.

- ✓ Ensuring proper **documentation and dissemination** (see *Chapter 3* below). Partners will ensure that each dataset is properly documented and tracked in order to effectively identify, manage and use data. To provide an accurate list of datasets held by the organization, a project catalogue of data should be compiled. This could be a collection of discovery level metadata for each dataset, in a form suitable for other partners to reference. These metadata should provide information about the content and accessibility of the data, together with contact details for further information about the data.

Figure 2: Schematics of the data management strategy.

3 SMART-ELECTRON DATA AND METADATA UNDER THE FAIR PRINCIPLE

3.1 STANDARDS, METADATA, PROTOCOLS, QUALITY PROCEDURE (BEST PRACTICES)

The research metadata from this project will be stored by each participant. The following table sums up the metadata format foreseen for each WP.

Type of Data	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6
Pdf	X	X	X	X	X	X
Doc/Docx	X	X	X	X	X	X
Ppt	X	X	X	X	X	X
Txt	X	X	X	X	X	X

Latex	X	X	X	X	X	
Xls/Xlsx						X
Jpeg	X	X	X	X	X	X
TIFF	X	X	X	X	X	X
Mp4						X
Mov						X

FINDABLE

The naming convention for metadata will be as follows:
 (Institution-name)-(Date format YYMMDD)-(reference sample or experiment set)-(reference data set)

Here we report the reference data set convention:

TEM-IMG transmission electron microscopy imaging experiment
 TEM-EELS transmission electron microscopy EELS experiment
 TEM-PINEM transmission electron microscopy PINEM experiment
 TEM-DIFF transmission electron microscopy diffraction experiment
 SLM spatial light modulator settings
 LIGHT laser light characterization experiment
 SEM scanning electron microscopy sample characterization
 FIB focused ion beam sample preparation
 THEO calculations or simulations
 ML machine learning or deep learning algorithm
 PELM photonic electron modulator design schemes and characterization experiments
 PREP-QU growth or preparation recipe for quantum materials
 PREP-EC growth or preparation recipe for electrochemical samples
 MEAS-EC electrochemical measurements
 PREP-BIO growth or preparation recipe for biological samples
 RAMSEY Ramsey-type holographic imaging experiment
 ESPI Electron-Single-Pixel-Imaging experiment
 Q-CL Quantum Cathodoluminescence experiment
 PAT FIB pattern / lithography mask

ACCESSIBLE

All the shared metadata within the SMART-electron Consortium will be provided in open format, i.e. in plain text format.

INTEROPERABLE

The SMART-electron project aims at collecting and documenting the data in a standardised way to ensure that the datasets can be understood, interpreted and shared in isolation alongside accompanying metadata and documentation.

Standard vocabularies for all metadata will be used by all the partners and beneficiaries as follows:

TEM experiment = experiment involving the use of a transmission electron microscope (imaging, spectroscopy or diffraction)

PINEM experiment = experiment involving the interaction of electron and light in a TEM

PELM design = design of the photonic-based electron modulator

PELM characterization = experiments characterizing the performance of the photonic-based electron modulator

SLM settings = sets of parameters driving the spatial light modulator

Optical characterization = images, spectra and time-correlation profiles of the laser light used in the experiments

Ramsey experiment = experiments based on a homodyne holographic detection scheme

ESPI experiment = experiments based on the use of structured electron profile for imaging

Q-CL experiment = experiments based on the use of structured electrons for enhanced light emission

Sample preparation = growth or fabrication of samples for the experiments to be conducted

Sample characterization = standard SEM and TEM analysis of the fabricated/prepared samples

Lithography and FIB = experiments involving the nanofabrication of phase masks

METADATA RE-USE

Metadata generated by SMART-electron are intended to be re-usable during and after the project by other researchers, Institutions, organisations and countries, once published. Unpublished results are considered confidential and their exchange/use/re-use within the network will be on a collaborative basis. SMART-electron data of potential IP interest or under IP protection will be made accessible/re-usable according to IP protection conditions.

3.2 STANDARDS, DATA, PROTOCOLS, QUALITY PROCEDURE (BEST PRACTICES)

The research data from this project will be stored by each participant. The following table sums up the data format foreseen for each WP.

Type of Data	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6
Pdf	X	X	X	X	X	X
Doc/Docx/Ods	X	X	X	X	X	X
Ppt	X	X	X	X	X	X
Txt	X	X	X	X	X	X
Xls/Xlsx/Odt	X	X	X	X	X	X
Jpeg	X	X	X	X	X	X
TIFF	X	X	X	X	X	X
Mp4	X	X	X	X	X	X
.mat, .fig., .m (matlab files)	X	X	X	X	X	
.py, .pyc, .pyd, .pyd (python files)	X	X		X		
.dm3, .dm4, .hdf5 (TEM files)	X	X	X	X	X	
.wl, .m (mathematica files)	X			X		
.FCStd (FreeCAD)		X		X		
.cpp (C++)	X					
.opj, .ogw, .ogg, .ogm (OriginLab)		X		X		
.hec, .csv (SLM configuration files)	X	X	X	X	X	
.dll, .exe, .html, .mat, .py, .png, .h5 (SLM SDK)		X	X	X	X	
.mph (comsol)	X	X	X	X	X	
.Mov, .Mxf, .wav, .aiff						X
.psd, .aep, .fcp, .avp, .avs, .avb						X

FINDABLE
<p>Each group has a naming convention to make data findable. The naming convention used by different groups will be described in section 3.</p>
ACCESSIBLE
<p>All the shared data within the Consortium will be provided in open format, i.e. in plain text or in format readable with open access software. All relevant data will be stored in a project repository on the Zenodo platform. We chose Zenodo because it supports the FAIR principles. The dataset underlining the corresponding publication will be made available at the same time of the publication. Zenodo implements long-term preservation features, notably bitstream preservation.</p> <p>Research shared data will be made available in a way that can be shared and easily reused by others. That means:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. sharing data using open file format (whenever possible), so that they can be implemented by both proprietary and open source software; 2. using format based on an underlying open standard; 3. using format which is interoperable among diverse internal and external platforms and applications; 4. using format which does not contain proprietary extensions (whenever possible).
INTEROPERABLE
<p>The SMART-electron project aims at collecting and documenting the data in a standardised way to ensure that, the datasets can be understood, interpreted and shared in isolation alongside accompanying metadata and documentation.</p> <p>Standard vocabularies for all metadata will be used by all the partners and beneficiaries as follows:</p> <p>TEM experiment = experiment involving the use of a transmission electron microscope (imaging, spectroscopy or diffraction)</p> <p>PINEM experiment = experiment involving the interaction of electron and light in a TEM</p> <p>PELM design = design of the photonic-based electron modulator</p> <p>PELM characterization = experiments characterizing the performance of the photonic-based electron modulator</p> <p>SLM settings = sets of parameters driving the spatial light modulator</p> <p>Optical characterization = images, spectra and time-correlation maps of the laser light used in the experiments</p> <p>Ramsey experiment = experiments based on a homodyne holographic detection scheme</p> <p>ESPI experiment = experiments based on the use of structured electron profile for imaging</p> <p>Q-CL experiment = experiments based on the use of structured electrons for enhanced light emission</p> <p>Sample preparation = growth or fabrication of samples for the experiments to be conducted</p>

<p>Sample characterization = standard SEM and TEM analysis of the fabricated/prepared samples</p> <p>Lithography and FIB = experiments involving the nanofabrication of phase masks</p>
<p>DATA RE-USE</p>
<p>Data generated by SMART-electron are intended to be re-usable during and after the project by other researchers, Institutions, organisations and countries, once published. Unpublished results are considered confidential and their exchange/use/re-use within the network will be on a collaborative basis. SMART-electron data of potential IP interest or under IP protection will be made accessible/re-usable according to IP protection conditions.</p>

4 DATA STORAGE, ARCHIVING, FORMAT, NAMING CONVENTION AND SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

<p>DATA STORAGE, ARCHIVING, FORMAT AND NAMING CONVENTION</p>		
<p>4.1 DATA STORAGE AND ARCHIVING PRACTICES</p>		
<p>Research data will be stored on specific partners servers and will be preserved for the long term in a project repository on the Zenodo platform. We chose Zenodo because it supports the FAIR principles. The dataset underlining the corresponding publication will be made available at the same time of the publication. Zenodo implements long-term preservation features, notably bitstream preservation.</p> <p>The groups have different policies regarding the data storage, data access, data transmission. All Dataset will be maintained for 5 years following project completion.</p> <p>Here is a description of the different practices.</p>		
<p>SHORT NAME</p>	<p>DATA STORAGE AND BACKUP</p>	<p>EXPECTED SIZE</p>
<p>UNIMIB</p>	<p>All data are stored on a local UNIMIB server and all relevant data will be also stored in a Zenodo repository; Dr. Vanacore is the owner of the local UNIMIB account and provides access and read/write permissions to the different members of the group. Data transmission can be performed with direct share of some file/folder.</p>	<p>~ 1 TB</p>
<p>EPFL</p>	<p>Data will be stored on the centralized file storage system managed by the EPFL Institute of Physics \atlas\LUMESgrp_publication_data. EPFL reference IT tech is Florence Hagen (Florence.hagen@epfl.ch). The central storage facility has redundancy, mirroring and is monitored. The frequency of data backup might change depending on the internal rules of the management and situation.</p> <p>The access to the data is managed through the EPFL identity management system, which is a secured system following the best practices in terms of identity</p>	<p>~ 1 TB</p>

	management. All the members of the research group are allowed to enter this storage with the same access rights.	
ICFO	ICFO will use the ICFO infrastructure to manage and store raw data providing access and read/write permissions to the different members of the group. ICFO will also use Zenodo as a repository to post published data.	~ 1 TB
TECHNION	All data are stored on the laboratory’s NAS server that has several backup drives running in parallel. Prof. Kaminer and the lab manager Dr. Fishman are in charge of the account and provide access and read/write permissions to the different members of the group. Final analysis results are also stored in the laboratory’s SharePoint, which receives ongoing support and backup by the Technion IT.	~ 1 TB
CNR	All data are stored on a shared cloud disk with local mirror; the data are owned jointly by the group. Data transmission can be performed by sharing options.	~ 1 TB
HOLOEYE	All Data for reports and SLM driving are stored on HOLOEYE’s intern File Server with a 3-fold backup. Mr. Olaya and Dr. Hermerschmidt are providing access to these data to the members of the groups through HOLOEYE Sharing System (NextCloud).	Up to 5 Tb
QED	All project deliverables for which QED is responsible are stored on GDrive with two local mirrors. Dr. LMC Giberti is the owner of the account and provides access and read/write permissions to the different members of the group. Data transmission can be performed via direct sharing of GDrive files/folders. All other used or generated files (e.g. media) are stored on local drives with triple back-up on 3 distinct physical supports, one of which is kept off-premises.	~ 1 TB

4.2 DATA FORMAT AND NAMING CONVENTIONS

The naming convention for data shared will be as follows:
(Institution-name)-(Date format YYYYMMDD)-(reference sample or experiment set)-(reference data set)

SHORT NAME	DATA FORMAT & SOFTWARE
UNIMIB	<p>Data will be generated/stored/shared in standard formats (such as Doc, xls, ppt, avi). The specific software/format/platforms used to generate/analyze specific activities such as TEM experiments, laser light characterization, PELM design, and sample characterization are all standard and available among the Consortium members. They will be specified in dedicated accompanying files explaining experimental details.</p> <p>- file .dm3, .dm4, .hdf5: electron detector files obtained during TEM experiments. They will contain either images, or spectra, or diffraction patterns. Naming convention: YYYYMMDD-(Sample Name)-TEM-(Measurement Type)-XXX, where: DD number of day, MM number of</p>

	<p>month, YYYY number of year; Measurement Type = IMG, EELS, PINEM or DIFF; and XXX is a progressive number for multiple acquisitions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - file .mat, .fig, and .m: Matlab files for data arrays (.mat), figures (.fig) and scripts (.m). Data analysis will be performed by exporting the raw data in .dm3, .dm4 or .hdf5 format into the Matlab environment. - file .txt, text file containing optical spectra and time-correlation profiles for laser light characterization collected using commercial photodiodes and optical spectrometers. YYYYMMDD-(Sample Name)-LIGHT-(Measurement Type)-XXX, where: DD number of day, MM number of month, YYYY number of year; Measurement Type = SPEC (spectrum) or TIME (time correlation profile); and XXX is a progressive number for multiple acquisitions. - file .txt, text file containing parameters related to growth or preparation recipe for electrochemical and biological samples. Naming convention: YYYYMMDD-(Sample Name)-PREP-EC-XXX or YYYYMMDD-(Sample Name)-PREP-BIO-XXX, where XXX is a progressive number for multiple acquisitions. - file .FCStd: FreeCAD files containing the design of mechanical pieces composing the photonic-based electron modulator. Naming convention: YYYYMMDD-PELM-(Part Name)-VersionXXX. - file .tiff: image files. Morphological characterization of electrochemical and biological samples will be performed via Scanning Electron Microscopy. YYYYMMDD-(Sample Name)-SEM-XXX, where: DD number of day, MM number of month, YYYY number of year; and XXX is a progressive number for multiple acquisitions. - files .opj, .ogw,.ogg, .ogm: OriginLab files for projects (.opj), workbooks (.ogw), graph (.ogg), and matrix(.ogm). These files will be used for electrochemistry data. Naming convention: YYYYMMDD-(Sample Name)-MEAS-EC-(Measurement Type)-XXX.
<p>EPFL</p>	<p>The data produced from this research project will be two-dimensional images collected by an electron-sensitive video-camera connected to a Transmission Electron Microscope. These images will represent:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Direct space contrast map of materials and nanostructures 2. Reciprocal-space images, also referred to as diffraction pattern from the materials investigated. 3. Energy-filtered images yielding Electron Energy Loss Spectroscopy data. <p>All of the raw data will be collected in the .dm2, .dm3 and .dm4 formats produced by Digital Micrograph, which is the standard acquisition software (version GMS 2.32) for most commercially-available electron microscopes. If needed, vendor-independent access to the raw data is possible thanks to a reverse-engineered technical format description</p>

	<p>available at https://www.ntu.edu.sg/home/cbb/info/dmformat/index.html. The data analysis will be carried out on .tiff images and matlab files (.mat or simple -ascii files containing 2D matrices of numbers).</p> <p>The data will be published on Zenodo which automatically provides a DOI for each separate dataset. They will be accompanied by the following contextual documentation:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Text files which detail the experimental procedures and instrumental parameters. 2. Files containing raw data in Digital Micrograph’s format (dm2, dm3, dm4, see above) and folders will be named according to a convention, which includes for each dataset, identifications to the researcher, the date, the study and the type of data. <p>For example: FirstAuthorNamePublication_yearDOI/Raw/Analyzed/Published</p> <p>The final dataset as deposited in the chosen data repository will also be accompanied by a README file listing the contents of the other files and outlining the file-naming convention used.</p>
<p>ICFO</p>	<p>Data will be generated/stored/shared in standard formats (such as Doc, xls, ppt, avi). The specific software/format/platforms used to generate/analyze specific activities such as theoretical calculations are all standard and available among the Consortium members. They will be specified in dedicated accompanying files explaining experimental details.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - file .cpp are C++ files containing routines/codes for running theoretical calculations, processing data and computing elements presented in our papers. - file .wl, .m are Mathematica files containing routines/codes for running theoretical calculations, processing data and computing elements presented in our papers. - file .txt, text files used for tables with tabulated functions for some simulations that are difficult to simulate. <p>Naming convention: YYYYMMDD-(Sample Name)-THEO-(Experiment Type)-XXX, where: DD number of day, MM number of month, YYYY number of year; Experiment Type = TEM-IMG, TEM-EELS, TEM-PINEM, TEM-DIFF, LIGHT, PELM, RAMSEY, ESPI, Q-CL; and XXX is a progressive number for multiple acquisitions.</p>
<p>TECHNION</p>	<p>Data will be generated, stored and shared in standard formats (such as Doc, xls, ppt, avi). The specific software and format used to generate and analyze specific experiments such as UTEM measurements, laser light characterization, PINEM experiments, and sample characterization, are all standard and available among the Consortium members. They will be specified in dedicated accompanying files explaining experimental details.</p>

	<p>- file .dm3, .dm4, .hdf5: electron detector files obtained during TEM experiments. They will contain either images, spectra, or diffraction patterns. Naming convention: YYYYMMDD-(Sample Name)-TEM-(Measurement Type)-XXX, where: DD number of day, MM number of month, YYYY number of year; Measurement Type = IMG, EELS, PINEM or DIFF; and XXX is a progressive number for multiple acquisitions.</p> <p>- file .mat, .fig, and .m: Matlab files for data arrays (.mat), figures (.fig) and scripts (.m). Data analysis will be performed by exporting the raw data in .dm3, .dm4 or .hdf5 format into the Matlab environment.</p> <p>- file .txt, text file containing optical spectra and time-correlation profiles for laser light characterization collected using commercial photodiodes and optical spectrometers. YYYYMMDD-(Sample Name)-LIGHT-(Measurement Type)-XXX, where: DD number of day, MM number of month, YYYY number of year; Measurement Type = SPEC (spectrum) or TIME (time correlation profile); and XXX is a progressive number for multiple acquisitions.</p> <p>- file .FCStd: FreeCAD files containing the design of mechanical pieces composing the photonic-based electron modulator. Naming convention: YYYYMMDD-PELM-(Part Name)-VersionXXX.</p> <p>- file .mat, .fig, and .m are Matlab files containing routines/codes for running theoretical calculations and processing theoretical data.</p> <p>- file .py, .pyc, .pyd, .pyd are Python files routines/codes for running theoretical calculations and processing theoretical data.</p> <p>Naming convention: YYYYMMDD-(Sample Name)-THEO-(Experiment Type)-XXX, where: DD number of day, MM number of month, YYYY number of year; Experiment Type = TEM-IMG, TEM-EELS, TEM-PINEM, TEM-DIFF, LIGHT, PELM, RAMSEY, ESPI, Q-CL; and XXX is a progressive number for multiple acquisitions.</p>
<p>CNR</p>	<p>Data will be generated/stored/shared in standard formats (such as Doc, xls, ppt, avi). The specific software/format/platforms used to generate/analyze specific activities such as TEM experiments, PELM design, and sample characterization are all standard and available among the Consortium members. They will be specified in dedicated accompanying files explaining experimental details.</p> <p>- file .dm3, (enriched TIF *): electron detector files obtained during TEM experiments. They will contain either images, or spectra, or diffraction patterns. Naming convention: YYYYMMDD-(Sample Name)-TEM-</p>

	<p>(Measurement Type)-XXX, where: DD number of day, MM number of month, YYYY number of year; Measurement Type = IMG, EELS, PINEM or DIFF; and XXX is a progressive number for multiple acquisitions.</p> <p><i>*Enriched TIF is a file used in STEM_CELL simulation where a 32bit float is contained as a tagged metafile of the image.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - file .mat, .fig, and .m: Matlab files for data arrays (.mat), figures (.fig) and scripts (.m). Data analysis will be performed by exporting the raw data in .dm3, format into the Matlab environment. - file .txt, our txt file are the stream files for the FIB pattern nanofabrication. Naming convention: YYYYMMDD-PAT-(Pattern Name)-XXX, where: DD number of day, MM number of month, YYYY number of year; Pattern Name indicates the type of nanofabricated pattern; and XXX is a progressive number for multiple runs. - File. dgs lithography mask fabrication details Naming convention: YYYYMMDD-PAT-(Pattern Name)-XXX, where: DD number of day, MM number of month, YYYY number of year; Pattern Name indicates the type of nanofabricated pattern; and XXX is a progressive number for multiple runs. -File .mph COMSOL projects for finite elements simulations. Naming convention: YYYYMMDD-THEO-(Project Name)-XXX, where: DD number of day, MM number of month, YYYY number of year; Project Name indicates the type of simulation; and XXX is a progressive number for multiple runs. - files .opj, .ogw,.ogg, .ogm: OriginLab files for projects (.opj). These files will be used for analyzing profiles and spectra.
<p>HOLOEYE</p>	<p>Data will be generated/stored/shared in standard formats (such as Doc, xls, ppt,). The specific software suite for driving the SLM in WP1, and the SLM configuration files (WP1, 2, 3, 4, 5) are property of HOLOEYE and will be provided to the group members (after registration, under user license). SDK-Files (.dll, .exe, .mat, .py, .png, .h5) for integration of the SLM in the systems of the group members (WP2, 3, 5 and 5) will be provided as well. Their use will be specified in dedicated accompanying files (.html).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - file .hec, .csv: SLM configuration files. They will contain the driving sequence (PCM) and the E-O calibration (Phase vs grey value). Naming convention: E-O calibration: TYPE_WL_Seq-Phase_LowV-HighV.csv, where: Type SLM type, WL nominal wavelength, Seq driving sequence,

	<p>Phase maximal achievable phase shift, LowV lower driving voltage, HighV high driving voltage; PCM driving sequence: N-M_descr.hec, where N-M sequence type, descr sequence description.</p> <p>- file .dll, .exe, .html, .mat, .py, .png, .h5: Software Development Kit files for integration of the SLM in the systems of the members of the group.</p>
<p>QED</p>	<p>Textual or text-like or printable files will be generated/stored/shared in standard formats (such as doc/docx, xls/xlsx, ppt/pptx, ods, odt, pdf). The specific software/format/platforms used to generate and edit such files are all standard and available among Consortium partners. Preference to open standards such as odt and ods will be given whenever this won't interfere with the workflow between partners.</p> <p>Deliverable names will follow this convention: SMART-electron_D(deliverable number)_(deliverable_name)_V(version number), e.g. SMART-electron_D6.1_Project__Logo_and_Webpage_First_Release_V1.0.pdf</p>

4.3 SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

The Consortium is committed in **assuring open access to scientific publications** (green or gold open access), meaning that any peer-reviewed scientific publication made within the context of the project will be available online to any user at no charge.

The two alternatives recommended by the EC to comply with this requirement are:

Self-archiving / 'green' OA: In this option, the beneficiaries deposit the final peer-reviewed manuscript in a repository of their choice. In this case, they must ensure open access to the publication within a maximum of six months (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities).

Open access publishing / 'gold' OA: In this option, researchers publish their results in open access journals, or in journals that sell subscriptions and also offer the possibility of making individual articles openly accessible via the payment of author processing charges (APCs) (hybrid journals). Again, open access via the chosen repository must be ensured upon publication.

Publications arising from the SMART-electron project will be made public preferably through the option of 'gold' OA in order to provide the widest dissemination of the published results through the own webpages of the publishers. In other cases, the scientific publications will be deposited in a repository ('green' OA). Most publishers allow to deposit a copy of the article in a repository, sometimes with a period of restricted access (embargo).

In Horizon 2020, the embargo period imposed by the publisher must be shorter than 6 months (or 12 months for social sciences and humanities). This embargo period will be therefore taken into account by the SMART-eelectron consortium to choose the open access modality for the fulfilment of the open access obligations established by the EC.

Additionally, according to the EC recommendation, whenever possible the SMART-electron consortium will retain the ownership of the copyright for their work through the use of a 'License to Publish', which is a publishing agreement between author and publisher. With this agreement, authors can retain copyright and the right to deposit the article in an Open Access repository, while

providing the publisher with the necessary rights to publish the article. Additionally, to ensure that others can be granted further rights for the use and reuse the work, the SMART-electron consortium may ask the publisher to release the paper under a Creative Commons license, preferably CC-0 or CC-BY .

Besides these two facts (retaining the ownership of the publication and effecting an embargo period), the SMART-electron consortium will also consider the relevance of the journal where the paper is intended to be published. SMART-electron aims and is expected to publish results in high impact-factor journals. Therefore, also this aspect will be taken into consideration when selecting the journals in which to publish the SMART-electron project results.

The journals to be considered for the SMART-electron publications mainly belong to the following publishers: AIP, ACS, APS, AAAS (Science), Nature Publishing Group, Elsevier, Wiley, PNAS, OPTICA (formerly OSA). These publishers have several scientific journals that allow an open access modality and/or the author to deposit a post-print version in a repository such as arXiv (<https://arxiv.org>). This is in line with the Horizon 2020 requirements. All the publications will acknowledge the project’s EU funding.

Finally, in the Model Grant Agreement, “scientific publications” mean primarily journal articles. Whenever possible, SMART-electron will provide access to other types of scientific publications such as presentations, public deliverables, etc.

5 DATA SHARING MECHANISMS, CONFIDENTIALITY, DATA PROTECTION AND SECURITY

5.1 DATA (MATERIAL) SHARING MECHANISMS AND PROCEDURES, CONFIDENTIALITY
DATA SHARING BETWEEN PARTNERS IN THE CONSORTIUM
Confidentiality issues are covered by the Consortium agreement.
DOCUMENT EXCHANGE TOOL
For Data/metadata/document exchange a server (e.g. Google Drive) will be used.
MATERIAL EXCHANGE (SAMPLES, PROTOTYPES, DEVICES...)
During the project, samples/reagents/materials will be exchanged among partners on a collaborative basis and under the signature of an MTA, when required. SMART-electron will encourage/favor the use of material available through the European Consortia, when possible.
DATA SHARING BETWEEN CONSORTIUM AND EU
Covered by the Consortium Agreement.
DATA SHARING BETWEEN CONSORTIUM MEMBERS AND THIRD PARTIES
To secure the confidentiality when exchanging data and materials relevant to the scope of SMART-electron we will use Non-disclosure agreements (NDA) and Material transfer agreement (MTA). All the beneficiaries should agree for the transfer.

5.2 DATA PROTECTION

SMART-electron data protection aspects will be coordinated according to the recommendations of the relevant national data protection authorities. The project is aware of the European data protection rules that have entered into force in May 2018 and their impact will be considered:

http://ec.europa.eu/justice/data-protection/reform/index_en.htm

H2020 open access policy stipulates that the information generated by the projects participating in that programme is made publicly available. However, as stated in EC guidelines on Data Management in H2020:

“As an exception, the beneficiaries do not have to ensure open access to specific parts of their research data if the achievement of the action’s main objective, as described in Annex I, would be jeopardised by making those specific parts of the research data openly accessible. In this case, the data management plan must contain the reasons for not giving access.”

In line with this, SMART-electron shall decide which data is made public according to aspects such as potential liabilities to commercialisation of technologies, related IPR protection (by patents or other forms of protection), risks with respect to achieving project objectives/outcomes, etc.

SMART-electron entails pioneering research that is of key importance to physics, materials science, nanomedicine, quantum information manipulation, and optics. Effective exploitation of SMART-electron research results depends on the proper management of intellectual property. To this end, the SMART-electron Consortium will adopt the following strategy (Figure 3):

Figure 3. Process for determining which information is to be made public (from EC’s document “Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020” – v3.2 – 21 March 2017)

If the research findings result in innovation or in significant new insights, the members of the consortium will consider two alternatives regarding protection, i.e.:

- to withhold the data for internal use or to apply for a patent in order to commercially exploit the invention and have in return financial gain; in the latter case, related publications will be therefore delayed until the patent filing;
- if said developments are not going to be withheld or patented, to publish results for knowledge-sharing purposes.

All intended dissemination or protection policies and actions are regulated by the SMART-electron Consortium Agreement. Once the relevant protections (e.g. IPR) are secured, SMART-electron partners may disseminate (subject to their legitimate interests) the obtained results and knowledge to the relevant scientific communities through contributions in journals and international conferences in the fields of physics, materials science, quantum technology, etc.

5.3 DATA SECURITY

For data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data) the following provisions will be in place:

- SMART-electron will store the processed/parsed results into Zenodo, which takes security issues very seriously;
- Zenodo servers are managed via OpenStack and Puppet configuration management system which ensures that the servers always have the latest security patches applied (<http://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure/>).